

Topological Spaces

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Abstract: The main objective of this study is to introduce a new class of closed sets namely Neutrosophic Nano RW-closed sets and Neutrosophic Nano RW-continuous functions in Neutrosophic Nano topological spaces. Some of its properties and interrelationship with some existing Neutrosophic nano closed sets have been discussed.

Keywords: N_N RW-closed set, N_N RW-open set, N_N RWT_{1/2} space, N_N RW-connected space, N_N RW-continuous, N_N RW-irresolute, N_N RW-open and N_N -closed maps.

1. Introduction

The theory of neutrosophic sets with three components namely, membership T (Truth), Indeterminacy I, and non-membership F (Falsehood), one of the interesting generalizations of theory of fuzzy sets and Intuitionistic fuzzy sets introduced by F.Smarandache [8]. In 2012, A.A. Salama and S.A. Alblowi [13] introduced and studied the theory of neutrosophic topological spaces. Since then several mathematicians contributed many papers to this area. Various results in ordinary topological spaces have been put in the neutrosophic setting, and also various departures have been observed. Neutrosophic set is a powerful tool to deal with indeterminate and inconsistent data. The concept of nano topology explored by M. Lellis Thivagar et. al[11] can be described as a collection of nano approximations for which equivalence classes are building blocks. In 2018, M. Lellis Thivagar et. al. [12] introduced a new concept called as Neutrosophic Nano topology and discussed neutrosophic nano interior and neutrosophic nano closure.

In 2007, S.S. Benchalli and R.S. Wali [4] introduced RW-closed sets in topological spaces. The authors D. Savithiri and C. Janaki [15] introduced the concept of Neutrosophic RW-closed sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces. In this article we introduce Neutrosophic Nano RW-closed sets and discuss some of its properties.

2 PRELIMINARIES

The following recalls requisite ideas and preliminaries necessary in the sequel of our work.

Definition 2.1:[9] Let X be a non-empty fixed set a Neutrosophic set (**NS for short**) A is an object having the form $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle, x \in X$ where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$, $\gamma_A(x)$ which represents the degree of membership function, the degree of indeterminacy and the degree of non-membership function respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Definition 2.2:[11] Let U be a non-empty finite set of objects called the universe and R be an equivalence relation on U named as the indiscernibility relation. Elements belonging to the same equivalence class are said to be indiscernible with one another. The pair (U, R) is said to be the approximation space. Let $X \subseteq U$.

(i) The lower approximation of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be classified as X with respect to R and it is denoted by $L_R(X)$. That is $L_R(X) = \bigcup_{x \in U} \{R(x) : R(x) \subseteq X\}$, where $R(x)$ denotes the equivalence class determined by x .

(ii) The upper approximation of X with respect to R is the set of all objects which can be possibly classified as X with respect to R and it is denoted by $U_R(X)$. That is $U_R(X) = \bigcup_{x \in U} \{R(x) : R(x) \cap X \neq \emptyset\}$.

(iii) The boundary region of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be classified neither as X nor as not X with respect to R and it is denoted by $B_R(X)$. That is $B_R(X) = U_R(X) - L_R(X)$.

Remark 2.3:[11]

(i) $L_R(X) \subseteq X \subseteq U_R(X)$.

(ii) $L_R(\emptyset) = U_R(\emptyset) = \emptyset$ and $L_R(U) = U_R(U) = U$.

(iii) $U_R(X \cup Y) = U_R(X) \cup U_R(Y)$.

(iv) $L_R(X \cap Y) = L_R(X) \cap L_R(Y)$.

(v) $U_R(X \cap Y) \subseteq U_R(X) \cap U_R(Y)$.

(vi) $L_R(X \cup Y) \supseteq L_R(X) \cup L_R(Y)$.

(vii) $L_R(X) \subseteq L_R(Y)$ and $U_R(X) \subseteq U_R(Y)$, whenever $X \subseteq Y$.

(viii) $U_R(X^c) = [L_R(X)]^c$ and $L_R(X^c) = [U_R(X)]^c$.

(ix) $U_R U_R(X) = L_R U_R(X) = U_R(X)$.

(x) $L_R L_R(X) = L_R U_R(X) = L_R(X)$.

Definition 2.4:[11] Let U be the universe, R be an equivalence relation on U and $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \emptyset, L_R(X), U_R(X), B_R(X)\}$ where $X \subseteq U$. $\tau_R(X)$ satisfies the following axioms:

(i) U and $\emptyset \in \tau_R(X)$.

(ii) The union of the elements of any sub-collection of $\tau_R(X)$ is in $\tau_R(X)$.

(iii) The intersection of the elements of any finite sub collection $\tau_R(X)$ is in $\tau_R(X)$.

That is, $\tau_R(X)$ forms a topology on U called the nano topology on U with respect to X . We call $(U, \tau_R(X))$ as the nano topological space. The elements of $\tau_R(X)$ are called nano-open sets.

Definition 2.5:[12] Let U be a non-empty set and R be an equivalence relation on U . Let S be a neutrosophic set in U with the membership function μ_S , the indeterminacy function σ_S , and the non-membership function γ_S . The neutrosophic nano lower, neutrosophic nano upper approximation and neutrosophic nano boundary of S in the approximation (U, R) denoted by $\underline{N}(S), \overline{N}(S)$ and $B(S)$ are respectively defined as follows:

$$(i) \underline{N}(S) = \{(x, \mu_{\underline{R}(A)}(x), \sigma_{\underline{R}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\underline{R}(A)}(x)) / y \in [x]_R, x \in U\}.$$

$$(ii) \overline{N}(S) = \{(x, \mu_{\overline{R}(A)}(x), \sigma_{\overline{R}(A)}(x), \gamma_{\overline{R}(A)}(x)) / y \in [x]_R, x \in U\}.$$

$$(iii) B(S) = \overline{N}(S) - \underline{N}(S).$$

where $\mu_{\underline{R}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in [x]_R} \mu_A(y)$, $\sigma_{\overline{R}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in [x]_R} \sigma_A(y)$, $\gamma_{\underline{R}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in [x]_R} \gamma_A(y)$,

$$\mu_{\overline{R}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in [x]_R} \mu_A(y), \sigma_{\overline{R}(A)}(x) = \bigvee_{y \in [x]_R} \sigma_A(y), \gamma_{\overline{R}(A)}(x) = \bigwedge_{y \in [x]_R} \gamma_A(y).$$

Definition 2.6:[12] Let U be an universe, R be an equivalence relation on U and S be a neutrosophic set in U and if the collection $\tau_N(S) = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}(S), \overline{N}(S), B(S)\}$ forms a topology then it is said to be a neutrosophic nano topology. We call $(U, \tau_N(S))$ as the neutrosophic nano topological space (**Briefly NNTS**). The elements of $\tau_N(S)$ are called as neutrosophic nano open (**In Short NNO**) sets.

Remark 2.7:[12] $[\tau_N(S)]^c$ is called as dual neutrosophic nano topology of $\tau_N(S)$. The elements of $[\tau_N(S)]^c$ are called neutrosophic nano closed (**In Short NNC**) sets.

Remark 2.8:[12] In neutrosophic nano topological space, the neutrosophic nano boundary cannot be empty. Since the difference between neutrosophic nano upper and neutrosophic nano lower approximations is defined as the maximum and minimum of the values in the neutrosophic sets.

Proposition 2.9:[12] Let U be a non-empty finite universe and S be a neutrosophic set on U . Then the following statements hold:

(i) The collection $\tau_N(S) = \{0_N, 1_N\}$, is the indiscrete neutrosophic nano topology on U .

(ii) If $\underline{N}(S) = \overline{N}(S) = B(S)$, then the neutrosophic nano topology, $\tau_N(S) = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}(S), B(S)\}$.

(iii) If $\underline{N}(S) = B(S)$, then $\tau_N(S) = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}(S), \overline{N}(S)\}$ is a neutrosophic nano topology.

(iv) If $\overline{N}(S) = B(S)$, then $\tau_N(S) = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}(S), B(S)\}$.

(v) The collection $\tau_N(S) = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}(S), \overline{N}(S), B(S)\}$ is the discrete neutrosophic nano topology on U

Definition 2.10:[12] Let $(U, \tau_N(S))$ be NNTS and $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x), x \in U \rangle$ be a NNS in X . Then the neutrosophic nano closure and neutrosophic nano interior of A are defined by

$$N_NCl(A) = \cap \{ K : K \text{ is a } N_NCS \text{ in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$$

$$N_NInt(A) = \cup \{ G : G \text{ is a } N_NOS \text{ in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}.$$

Definition 2.11:[12] A subset A of a neutrosophic nano topological space Let $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is said to be

(i) a neutrosophic nano pre closed (**N_N pre-closed**) set if $N_NCl(N_NInt(A)) \subseteq A$.

(ii) a neutrosophic nano semi-closed (**N_N semi-closed**) set if $N_NInt(N_NCl(A)) \subseteq A$.

(iii) a neutrosophic nano regular open (**In short N_NRO**) set if $A = N_NInt(N_NCl(A))$ and regular closed (**In short N_NRC**) set if $A = N_NCl(N_NInt(A))$.

(iv) a neutrosophic regular semi open (**In short N_NRSO**) if there exists a N_NRO set U such that $U \subseteq A \subseteq N_NCl(A)$

(v) a neutrosophic nano α -closed (**$N_N\alpha$ -closed**) set if $N_NCl(N_NInt(N_NCl(A))) \subseteq A$.

(vi) a neutrosophic nano g -closed (**N_Ng -closed**) set if $N_NCl(A) \subseteq F$ whenever $A \subseteq F$ and F is N_NO in U .

Definition 2.11:[6] The difference between two neutrosophic nano sets A and B is defined as

$$A \setminus B(S) = \{x, \min [(\mu_A(x), \gamma_B(x)), \min [(\sigma_A(x), 1 - \sigma_B(x)), \max [\gamma_A(x), \mu_B(x)]]].$$

3. NEUTROSOPHIC NANO RW-CLOSED SETS

Definition 3.1: A subset A of a neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is called as neutrosophic nano regular weakly closed (**In short N_NRW -closed**) set, if $N_NCl(A) \subseteq V$ whenever $A \subseteq V$ and V is a neutrosophic nano regular open in U .

Definition 3.2: The neutrosophic nano RW -closure and neutrosophic nano RW -interior of A are defined by

$$N_NRWCl(A) = \cap \{ K : K \text{ is a } N_NRWCS \text{ in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K \}$$

$$N_NRWInt(A) = \cup \{ G : G \text{ is a } N_NRWOS \text{ in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A \}.$$

Definition 3.3: (i) neutrosophic nano RG - Closed set (**shortly N_NRG – closed set**) of X if there exists a neutrosophic nano regular open set U such that $N_NCl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$.

(ii) neutrosophic nano RWG - closed set (**shortly N_NRWG – closed set**) of X if there exists a neutrosophic nano regular open set U such that $N_NCl(N_NInt(A)) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$.

(iii) neutrosophic nano W-closed set (**shortly N_NW – closed set**) of X if there exists a neutrosophic nano semi-open set U such that $N_NCl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$.

(iv) neutrosophic nano g-closed set (**shortly N_NG – closed set**) of X if there exists a neutrosophic open set U such that $N_NCl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$.

Proposition 3.3: (i) Every N_N -closed set is N_NRW -closed.

(ii) Every N_N - regular closed set is N_NRW -closed.

(iii) Every N_N - π closed set is N_NRW -closed.

(iv) Every N_NW -closed set is N_NRW -closed.

Proof: Follows from [4].

The following example makes clear that the converse of the Proposition 3.3 need not be true.

Example 3.4: Let $U = \{p_1, p_2, p_3\}$ be the universe set and the equivalence relation $U \setminus R = \{\{p_1, p\}, \{p_2\}\}$. Let

$S = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.1,0.6,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$ be a neutrosophic nano subset of U. Then $\overline{N}(S) =$

$\left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.1,0.6,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $\underline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $B(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.1,0.6,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$. So the

neutrosophic nano topology $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}, B\}$ where the neutrosophic closed sets are $\tau_N^C =$

$\{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}^C, B^C\}$. Let $Q_1 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.2,0.1,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.3,0.1,0.2)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle \right\}$, then Q_1 is N_NRW -closed but it is not an

N_N -closed set in U. $Q_2 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.2,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.3,0.6,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.2,0.3,0.3)} \right\rangle \right\}$, Q_2 is N_NRW -closed but it is neither N_N

Regular-closed nor $N_N\pi$ -closed set and $Q_3 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.1,0.3,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.2,0.6,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.6)} \right\rangle \right\}$, then Q_3 is

N_NRW -closed but not N_NW -closed set.

Proposition 3.5: (i) Every N_NRW -closed set is N_NRG -closed.

(ii) Every N_NRW -closed set is N_NGPR -closed.

(iii) Every N_NRW -closed set is N_NRWG -closed.

Proof: Follows from [4].

The converse of the Proposition 3.4 need not be true.

Example 3.6: * Let $U = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, p_5\}$ be the universe set and the equivalence relation $U \setminus R =$

$\{\{p_1, p_3\}, \{p_2\}, \{p_4, p_5\}\}$. Let $S = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.4,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.5,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.6,0.3,0.1)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.5,0.3,0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$ be a

neutrosophic nano subset of U $\overline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.5,0.3,0.2)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4, p_5}{(0.6,0.3,0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $\underline{N}(S) =$

$\left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.4, 0.3, 0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4, p_5}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $B(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.4, 0.3, 0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4, p_5}{(0.1, 0.3, 0.6)} \right\rangle \right\}$. The neutrosophic

nano topology $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}, \overline{N}, B\}$. Let $R_1 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.3, 0.3, 0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.2, 0.3, 0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.2, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.1, 0.2, 0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.1, 0.3, 0.8)} \right\rangle \right\}$.

Then R_1 is both N_N GPR-closed and N_N RWG – closed but it is not an N_N RW-closed.

* In example 3.4, let $R_2 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.3, 0.7, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.3, 0.4, 0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.2, 0.5, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.1, 0.5, 0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.1, 0.6, 0.7)} \right\rangle \right\}$, then R_2 is N_N RG-closed but not an N_N RW-closed.

Proposition 3.7: The finite union of N_N RW – closed subsets of U is also an N_N RW – closed subset of U .

Proof: Assume that P and Q are N_N RW – closed sets in U . Let R be an N_N RSO set in X such that $P \cup Q \subseteq R$. Then $P \subseteq R$ and $Q \subseteq R$. Since P and Q are N_N RW – closed sets, N_N Cl(P) $\subseteq R$ and N_N Cl(Q) $\subseteq R$. Then N_N Cl($P \cup Q$) = N_N Cl(P) $\cup N_N$ Cl(Q) $\subseteq R$. Hence $P \cup Q$ is an N_N RW – closed set in U .

Remark 3.8: The intersection of two N_N RW-closed sets in $(U, \tau_N(S))$ need not be an N_N RW-closed set in U .

Example 3.9: Let $U = \{p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, p_5\}$ be the universe set and the equivalence relation $U \setminus R =$

$\{\{p_1, p_3\}, \{p_2\}, \{p_4, p_5\}\}$. Let $S = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.4, 0.3, 0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.6, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$ be a neutrosophic

nano subset of $U \overline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.2)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4, p_5}{(0.6, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $\underline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.4, 0.3, 0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4, p_5}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$

and $B(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1, p_3}{(0.4, 0.3, 0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4, p_5}{(0.1, 0.3, 0.6)} \right\rangle \right\}$. The neutrosophic nano topology $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}, \overline{N}, B\}$.

$R_1 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.6, 0.3, 0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.5, 0.3, 0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.5, 0.2, 0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.3, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.4, 0.4, 0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $R_2 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.2, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.3, 0.5, 0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.2, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle,$

$\left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.1, 0.5, 0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.1, 0.7, 0.6)} \right\rangle \right\}$. Then R_1 and R_2 are N_N RW-closed sets but $R_1 \cap R_2$ is not an N_N RW-closed set.

Proposition 3.10: If a subset A of U is N_N RW – closed set in U , then N_N Cl(A) \setminus A does not contain any non-empty neutrosophic nano regular semi-open set in U .

Proof: Suppose that A is an N_N RW – closed set in U . We shall prove by contradiction. Let R be an N_N RSO set such that N_N Cl(A) \setminus $A \supset R$ which implies $R \subseteq U \setminus A$ i.e., $A \subseteq U \setminus R$. Since R is N_N RSO, $U \setminus R$ is also N_N RSO set in U . Since A is an N_N RW – closed set, N_N Cl(A) $\subseteq U \setminus R$. So $R \subseteq U \setminus N_N$ Cl(A) also $R \subseteq N_N$ Cl(A) implies $R = \phi$. Hence N_N Cl(A) \setminus A does not contain any non-empty N_N RSO set in U .

The converse of the Proposition 3.10 need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 3.11: In example 3.9, in the neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$, let $A =$

$\left\{ \left\langle \frac{p_1}{(0.3, 0.2, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_2}{(0.3, 0.2, 0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_3}{(0.2, 0.3, 0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_4}{(0.1, 0.2, 0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{p_5}{(0.1, 0.3, 0.8)} \right\rangle \right\}$, then N_N Cl(A) \setminus A does not contain any

non-empty N_N RSO set, but A is not an N_N RW-closed set in U .

Corollary 3.12: If a subset A of U is N_{NRW} – closed set in U , then $N_{NCl}(A) \setminus A$ does not contain any non-empty neutrosophic nano regular- open set in U .

Proof: Follows from the Proposition 3.10 and the fact that every N_{NRO} set is N_{NRSO} in U .

Proposition 3.13: If A is N_{NRO} and N_{NRW} -closed, then A is N_{NRC} set and hence N_{N} -clopen.

Proof: Suppose A is N_{NRO} and N_{NRW} – closed. As every N_{NRO} set is N_{NRSO} and $A \subseteq A$, we have $N_{NCl}(A) \subseteq A$. Also $A \subseteq N_{NCl}(A)$, thus $N_{NCl}(A) = A$. Hence A is a N_{NC} set. Since A is N_{NRO} it is N_{NO} set. Now $N_{NCl}(N_{NInt}(A)) = N_{NCl}(A) = A$. Therefore A is N_{NRC} and Neutrosophic nano clopen.

Proposition 3.14: If A is an N_{NRW} – closed subset of U such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq N_{NCl}(A)$, then B is an N_{NRW} – closed set in U .

Proof: Let A be an N_{NRW} – closed set of U such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq N_{NCl}(A)$. Let R be N_{NRSO} set of U such that $B \subseteq R$. Then $A \subseteq R$. Since A is N_{NRW} –closed set, we have $N_{NCl}(A) \subseteq R$ and $N_{NCl}(B) \subseteq N_{NCl}(N_{NCl}(A)) \subseteq R$. Therefore B is also an N_{NRW} – closed set in U .

The following example shows that the converse of the Proposition 3.13 need not be true.

Example 3.15: Let $U = \{n_1, n_2, n_3\}$ be the universe set and the equivalence relation $U \setminus R = \{\{n_1, n_3\}, \{n_2\}\}$.

Let $S = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{x_1}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_3}{(0.1,0.6,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$ be a neutrosophic nano subset of U . Then $\overline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{x_1, x_3}{(0.1,0.6,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $\underline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{x_1, x_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $B(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{x_1, x_3}{(0.1,0.6,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$. So the neutrosophic nano topology $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}, B\}$ and the neutrosophic closed sets are $\tau_N^C = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}^C, B^C\}$. Let $A = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{x_1}{(0.1,0.3,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_2}{(0.2,0.6,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.6)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $B = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{x_1}{(0.2,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_2}{(0.3,0.6,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{x_3}{(0.2,0.3,0.3)} \right\rangle \right\}$. Then A and B are N_{NRW} -closed sets in $(U, \tau_N(S))$, but $A \subseteq B$ is not a subset of $N_{NCl}(A)$.

Proposition 3.16: Let A be an N_{NRW} -closed in $(U, \tau_N(S))$. Then A is N_N -closed if and only if $N_{NCl}(A) \setminus A$ is N_{NRSO} .

Proof: Let A be an N_N -closed in $(U, \tau_N(S))$. Then $N_{NCl}(A) \setminus A = \phi$ which is N_{NRSO} .

Conversely, suppose $N_{NCl}(A) \setminus A$ is N_{NRSO} in U . By hypothesis, A is N_{NRW} -closed implies $N_{NCl}(A) \setminus A$ does

not contain any non-empty N_{NRSO} in U . Then $N_{NCl}(A) \setminus A = \phi$ which implies that A is N_N -closed in U .

Proposition 3.17: If A is N_{NRO} and N_{NRG} closed, then A is N_{NRW} -closed in U .

Proof: Let A be an N_{NRO} and N_{NRG} -closed. Let Q be any N_{NRSO} set in U such that $A \subseteq Q$. since A is N_{NRO} and N_{NRG} we have $N_{NCl}(A) \subseteq A \subseteq Q$. Therefore A is N_{NRW} -closed.

Proposition 3.18: If a subset A of a neutrosophic nano topological space U is both N_N RSO and N_N RW-closed, then it is N_N -closed.

Proof: Suppose A be a subset of a neutrosophic nano topological space U is both N_N RSO and N_N RW-closed. Then $A \subset A$ and $N_NCl(A) \subseteq A$ which implies A is N_N -closed.

Remark 3.19: The concept of N_N RW-closed set is independent with the concepts of (i) N_N semi –closed (ii) N_N RW-preclosed (iii) $N_N\alpha$ -closed (iv) N_N WG - closed sets which is shown by the following example.

Example 3.20: Let $U = \{n_1, n_2, n_3\}$ be the universe set. $U \setminus R = \{\{n_1\}, \{n_2, n_3\}\}$ be an equivalence relation.

Let $S = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.3,0.4,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.6,0.4,0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$ be a neutrosophic nano subset of U . Then $\overline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1, n_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.6,0.4,0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $\underline{N}(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1, n_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.3,0.4,0.5)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $B(S) = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1, n_3}{(0.1,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.1,0.4,0.6)} \right\rangle \right\}$. So the neutrosophic nano topology $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, \underline{N}, \overline{N}, B\}$. In the neutrosophic nano topology $(U, \tau_N(S))$,

- Let $A = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.2,0.5,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.1,0.5,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.1,0.4,0.7)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $B = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.2,0.7,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.5,0.6,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.4,0.5,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$, then A is N_N semi-closed but not an N_N RW-closed and B is N_N RW-closed but it is not an N_N semi-closed.
- Let $C = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.1,0.2,0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.3,0.3,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.1,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $D = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.1,0.4,0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.1,0.6,0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.3,0.4,0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$, then C is both N_N pre-closed set and N_N WG-closed but not an N_N RW-closed and D is N_N RW-closed but it is neither N_N pre-closed nor an N_N WG-closed sets.
- In example 3.8, in the topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$, $E = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.6,0.3,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.5,0.3,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.5,0.2,0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_4}{(0.3,0.3,0.1)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_5}{(0.4,0.4,0.1)} \right\rangle \right\}$ and $F = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.3,0.3,0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.2,0.3,0.6)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.2,0.3,0.5)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_4}{(0.1,0.2,0.7)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_5}{(0.1,0.3,0.8)} \right\rangle \right\}$, E is N_N RW-closed set but not an $N_N\alpha$ -closed set and F is $N_N\alpha$ -closed but it is not an N_N RW-closed set.

Proposition 3.21: If an N_N subset A is both N_N -open and N_N G-closed in $(U, \tau_N(S))$, then it is N_N RW-closed in U .

Proof: Let A be N_N -open and N_N G-closed in U . Let $A \subset U$ and U be an N_N RSO in U . Now, $A \subset A$. By hypothesis, $N_NCl(A) \subset U$. Thus A is N_N RW-closed.

Remark 3.22: If A is both N_N -open and N_N RW-closed in U , then A need not be N_N G-closed in general which is shown in the following example.

Example 3.23: In example 3.8, the N_N -open set B is N_N RW-closed but it is not an N_N G-closed set.

The above discussions are implicated in the following diagram.

- 1. N_N RW-closed 2. N_N -closed 3. N_N R-closed 4. $N_N\pi$ -closed 5. N_N RG-closed
- 6. N_N RWG-closed 7. N_N GPR-closed 8. N_N semi-closed 9. N_N pre-closed
- 10. $N_N\alpha$ -closed 11. N_N WG-closed.

Proposition 3.24: If a subset A of a neutrosophic nano topological space U is both N_N -open and N_N WG-closed, then it is N_N RW-closed.

Proof: Suppose a subset A of U is both N_N -open and N_N WG-closed. Let $A \subset U$ and U is N_N RSO. Then $N_NCl(N_NInt(A)) = A \subset A$, since A is N_N -open. Hence $N_NCl(A) \subset U$ implies that A is an N_N RW-closed in U .

Definition 3.25: A neutrosophic nano subset A of a neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is called an N_N RW-open if and only if its complement A^c is N_N RW-closed.

Proposition 3.26: An N_N set A of a topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is N_N RW-open if $F \subseteq N_NInt(A)$ whenever F is N_N RSO and $F \subset A$.

Proof: Follows from the definition 3.1.

Proposition 3.27: Let A be an N_N RW-open set of neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ and $N_NInt(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$. Then B is N_N RW-open.

Proof: Suppose that A is an N_N RW-open in U and $N_NInt(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$ implies $A^c \subseteq B^c \subseteq N_NCl(A^c)$. Since A^c is N_N RW-closed, by Proposition 3.14, B^c is N_N RW-closed. Hence B is N_N RW-open.

Proposition 3.28: Let $(U, \tau_N(S))$ be a neutrosophic nano topological space and N_N RSO(X) and N_N C(X) be the family of all N_N RSO sets and N_N C sets respectively. Then N_N RSO(X) \subseteq N_N C(X) if and only if every

neutrosophic nano set of U is N_NRW -closed.

Proof: Necessity: Suppose that $N_NRSO(X) \subseteq N_NC(X)$ and let A be an N_N -set of U such that $A \subseteq R \in N_NRSO(X)$. Then $N_NCl(A) \subseteq N_NCl(R) = R$, by hypothesis. Hence $N_NCl(A) \subseteq R$ when $A \subseteq R$ and R is N_NRSO which implies that A is N_NRW -closed.

Sufficiency: Assume that every neutrosophic nano set of U is N_NRW -closed. Let $R \in N_NRSO(X)$. Then since $R \subseteq R$ and R is N_NRW -closed, $N_NCl(R) \subseteq R$ then $R \in N_NCl(X)$. Therefore $N_NRSO(X) \subseteq N_NCl(X)$.

Definition 3.29: A neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is called as N_NRW -connected if there is no proper N_N -subset of U which is both N_NRW -open N_NRW -closed.

Proposition 3.30: Every N_NRW -connected space is N_N -connected.

Proof: Let $(U, \tau_N(S))$ be an N_NRW -connected and suppose that $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is not N_N -connected. Then there exists a proper N_N -set A ($A \neq 0_N, A \neq 1_N$) such that A is both N_N -open and N_N -closed set. Since every N_N -open and N_N -closed set is N_NRW -open and N_NRW -closed, $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is not an N_NRW -connected which is a contradiction. This shows that U is N_N -connected.

Proposition 3.31: A N_NT space is N_NRW -connected if and only if there exists no non-zero N_NRW -open sets A and B in X such that $A = B^c$.

Proof: Necessity: Suppose that A and B are N_NRW -open sets such that $A \neq 0_N \neq B$, and $A = B^c$. Since $B = A^c$, A is N_NRW -closed set and $B \neq 0_N$ implies $B^c \neq 1_N$, i.e., $A \neq 1_N$. Hence there exists a proper N_N -set A which is both N_NRW -open and N_NRW -closed which is a contradiction to the fact that U is N_NRW -connected.

Sufficiency: Let $(U, \tau_N(S))$ be an N_NTS and A is both N_NRW -open and N_NRW -closed set in U such that $0_N \neq A \neq 1_N$. Take $B = A^c$ implies that B is N_NRW -open and $A \neq 1_N \Rightarrow B = A^c \neq 0_N$ which is a contradiction. Hence there is no proper N_N -subset of U which is both N_NRW -open and N_NRW -closed. Therefore $N_NTS (U, \tau_N(S))$ is N_NRW -connected.

Definition 3.32: A neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is said to be an $N_NRWT_{1/2}$ -space if every N_NRW -closed set in U is N_N -closed in U .

Proposition 3.33: A neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is $N_NRWT_{1/2}$ space, then the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) U is N_NRW -connected (ii) U is N_N -connected.

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Follows from the Proposition 3.29.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i): Assume that U is $N_NRWT_{1/2}$ -space, and N_N -connected. Suppose that U is not an N_NRW -connected, then there exists a proper N_N -set A which is both N_NRW -open and N_NRW -closed. Since $(U, \tau_N(S))$ is $N_NRWT_{1/2}$, A is both N_N -open and N_N -closed which is a contradiction to the fact that U is N_N -connected. This shows that U is N_NRW -connected.

4. N_N RW-CONTINUOUS FUNCTIONS

Definition 4.1: (i) A function $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is said to be a neutrosophic nano RW-continuous (**In short N_N RW-continuous**) if the inverse image of N_N -closed set of V is N_N RW-closed in $(U, \tau_N(S))$.

(ii) A function $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is said to be a neutrosophic nano RW-irresolute (**In short N_N RW-irresolute**) if the inverse image of N_N RW-closed set of V is N_N RW-closed in $(U, \tau_N(S))$.

Proposition 4.2: A mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-continuous if and only if the inverse image of every N_N -open set of V is N_N RW-open in U .

Proof: It is obvious because $f^{-1}(A^c) = [f^{-1}(A)]^c$ for every N_N -set A of V .

Proposition 4.3: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-continuous, then $f(N_NRWCl(A)) \subseteq N_NCl(f(A))$ for every N_N -set A of U .

Proof: Let A be an N_N -set of U . Then $N_NCl(f(A))$ is an N_N -closed set of V . Since f is an N_N RW-continuous function, $f^{-1}(N_NCl(f(A)))$ is N_N RW-closed in U . Clearly $A \subseteq f^{-1}(N_NCl(f(A)))$. Therefore $N_NRWCl(A) \subseteq N_NRWCl(f^{-1}(N_NCl(f(A)))) = f^{-1}(N_NCl(f(A)))$. Hence $f(N_NRWCl(A)) \subseteq N_NCl(f(A))$ for every N_N -set A of U .

Proposition 4.4: (i) Every N_N -continuous map is N_N RW-continuous.

(ii) Every N_N - regular continuous map is N_N RW-continuous.

(iii) Every N_N - π -continuous set is N_N RW-continuous.

(iv) Every N_N W-continuous map is N_N RW-continuous.

(v) Every N_N RW-irresolute map is N_N RW-continuous.

Proof: Obvious.

Remark 4.4: The following example makes clear that the converse of the Proposition 4.4 may not be true.

Example 4.5: Let $U = \{n_1, n_2, n_3\} = V$ be the universe sets. $U \setminus R_1 = \{\{n_1\}, \{n_2, n_3\}\}$ and $U \setminus R_2 = \{\{n_1, n_3\}, \{n_2\}\}$ be equivalence relations. Let $S_1 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.3, 0.4, 0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.6, 0.3, 0.1)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.2, 0.6, 0.2)} \right\rangle \right\}$, $S_2 = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{n_1}{(0.1, 0.2, 0.3)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_2}{(0.2, 0.3, 0.4)} \right\rangle, \left\langle \frac{n_3}{(0.1, 0.6, 0.4)} \right\rangle \right\}$ be a neutrosophic nano subsets of U . Then $\tau_N(S_1) = \{0_N, \overline{N}(S_1), \underline{N}(S_1), B(S_1), 1_N\}$, $\tau_N(S_2) = \{0_N, \overline{N}(S_2), B(S_2), 1_N\}$ be the neutrosophic nano topologies on U and V respectively. Define an identity map $f: (U, \tau_N(S_1)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(S_2))$. Then f is N_N RW-continuous but is neither N_N -continuous nor N_N W-continuous. Similarly it's not an N_N R-continuous, $N_N\pi$ -continuous and N_N RW-irresolute.

Proposition 4.6: (i) Every N_N RW-continuous map is N_N RG-continuous.

(ii) Every N_N RW- continuous map is N_N GPR- continuous.

(iii) Every N_N RW- continuous map is N_N RWG- continuous.

Proposition 4.7: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-continuous and $g: (V, \tau_N(T)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N -continuous. Then $g \circ f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RW-continuous.

Proof: Let A be an N_N -closed in W . Then $g^{-1}(A)$ is N_N -closed in V , because g is N_N -continuous. Therefore $(g \circ f)^{-1}(A) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A))$ is N_N RW-closed in U . Hence $g \circ f$ is N_N RW-continuous.

Proposition 4.8: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-continuous and $g: (V, \tau_N(T)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N G-continuous and $(V, \tau_N(T))$ is $N_N T_{1/2}$ then $g \circ f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RW-continuous.

Proof: Let A be an N_N -closed set in W , then $g^{-1}(A)$ is N_N G-closed in V . Since V is $N_N T_{1/2}$ then $g^{-1}(A)$ is N_N -closed in V . Hence, $(g \circ f)^{-1}(A) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A))$ is N_N RW-closed in U . Hence $g \circ f$ is N_N RW-continuous.

Proposition 4.9: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RG - irresolute and $g: (V, \tau_N(V)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RW-continuous, then $g \circ f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RG-continuous.

Proof: Let A be an N_N -closed set in W , then $g^{-1}(A)$ is N_N RW-closed in V , since g is N_N RW-continuous. Every N_N RW-closed set is N_N RG-closed, $g^{-1}(A)$ is N_N RG-closed set in V . Then $(g \circ f)^{-1}(A) = f^{-1}(g^{-1}(A))$ is N_N RG-closed in U , by hypothesis. Hence $g \circ f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RG-continuous.

Proposition 4.10: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-continuous surjection and U is N_N RW-connected then V is N_N -connected.

Proof: Assume that V is not an N_N -connected space. Then there exists a proper N_N -subset F of V which is both N_N -open and N_N -closed. Therefore, by hypothesis, $f^{-1}(F)$ is a proper N_N -set of U which is both N_N RW-open and N_N RW-closed in U implies that U is not an N_N RW-connected which is a contradiction. This shows that V is N_N -connected.

Definition 4.11: (i) A mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is said to be N_N RW-open map if the image of every N_N -open set of U is N_N RW-open set in V .

(ii) A mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is said to be N_N RW-closed map if the image of every N_N -closed set of U is N_N RW-closed set in V .

Proposition 4.12: A mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-open if and only if for every N_N -set A of U , $f(N_N \text{Int}(A)) \subseteq N_N \text{RW Int}(f(A))$.

Proof: Necessity: Let f be an N_N RW-open map and A is an N_N -open set in U , $N_N \text{Int}(A) \subseteq A$ which implies that $f(N_N \text{Int}(A)) \subseteq f(A)$. Since f is an N_N RW-open mapping, $f(N_N \text{Int}(A))$ is N_N RW-open set in V such that $f(N_N \text{Int}(A)) \subseteq f(A)$. Therefore $f(N_N \text{Int}(A)) \subseteq N_N \text{RW Int } f(A)$.

Sufficiency: Suppose that A is an N_N -open set of U . Then $f(A) = f(N_N \text{Int}(A)) \subseteq N_N \text{RW Int } f(A)$. But $N_N \text{RW Int } (f(A)) \subseteq f(A)$. Consequently $f(A) = N_N \text{RW Int}(A)$ which implies that $f(A)$ is an N_N RW-open set of V and hence f is an N_N RW-open map.

Proposition 4.13: A mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-open if and only if for every neutrosophic nano set A of V and for each N_N -closed set B of U containing $f^{-1}(A)$ there is a N_N RW-closed set F of V such that $A \subseteq F$ and $f^{-1}(F) \subseteq B$.

Proof: Necessity: Suppose that f is N_N RW-open map. Let A be a N_N -closed set of V and B be a N_N C set of U such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq B$. Then $F = f^{-1}(B^c)$ is a N_N RW-closed set of V such that $f^{-1}(F) \subseteq B$.

Sufficiency: Let F be a N_N O set of U . Then $f^{-1}(f(F))^c \subseteq F^c$ and F^c is a N_N C set in X . By hypothesis there is an N_N RW-closed set G of V such that $(f(F))^c \subseteq G$ and $f^{-1}(G) \subseteq F^c$. Therefore $F \subseteq (f^{-1}(G))^c$. Hence $G^c \subseteq f(F) \subseteq f((f^{-1}(G))^c) \subseteq G^c$ i.e., $f(F) = G^c$ which is N_N RW-open in V and thus f is N_N RW-open map.

Proposition 4.14: If a mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-open, then $N_N \text{Int}(f^{-1}(G)) \subseteq f^{-1}(N_N \text{RWInt}(G))$ for every neutrosophic nano set G of Y .

Proof: Let G be neutrosophic nano set of V . Then $N_N \text{Int}f^{-1}(G)$ is a N_N O set in U . Since f is N_N RW-open $f(N_N \text{Int}f^{-1}(G)) \subseteq N_N \text{RWInt}(f(f^{-1}(G))) \subseteq N_N \text{RWInt}(G)$. Thus $N_N \text{Int}(f^{-1}(G)) \subseteq f^{-1}(N_N \text{RWInt}(G))$.

Proposition 4.15: A mapping $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N RW-closed if and only if for every neutrosophic nano set A of V and for each N_N O set B of U containing $f^{-1}(A)$ there is a N_N RW-open set F of V such that $A \subseteq F$ and $f^{-1}(F) \subseteq B$.

Proof: Necessity: Suppose that f is N_N RW-closed map. Let A be a N_N C set of V and B be a N_N O set of U such that $f^{-1}(A) \subseteq B$. Then $F = V \setminus f^{-1}(B^c)$ is a N_N RW-open set of V such that $f^{-1}(F) \subseteq B$.

Sufficiency: Let F be a N_N C set of X . Then $f^{-1}(f(F))^c \subseteq F^c$ and F^c is a N_N O set in U . By hypothesis there is an N_N RW-open set R of V such that $(f(F))^c \subseteq R$ and $f^{-1}(R) \subseteq F^c$. Therefore $F \subseteq (f^{-1}(R))^c$. Hence $R^c \subseteq f(F) \subseteq f((f^{-1}(R))^c) \subseteq R^c$ i.e., $f(F) = R^c$ which is N_N RW-closed in V . Thus f is N_N RW-closed map.

Proposition 4.16: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N -almost irresolute and N_N RW-closed map. If A is N_N RW-closed set of U , then $f(A)$ is N_N RW-closed in V .

Proof: Let $f(A) \subseteq R$ where R is an N_N RSO set of V . since f is an N_N -almost irresolute, $f^{-1}(R)$ is an N_N SO set of U such that $A \subseteq f^{-1}(R)$. Since A is N_N W-closed set of U which implies that $N_N \text{Cl}(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(R) \Rightarrow f(N_N \text{Cl}(A)) \subseteq R$, i.e., $N_N \text{Cl}(f(N_N \text{Cl}(A))) \subseteq R$. Therefore $N_N \text{Cl}(f(A)) \subseteq R$ whenever $f(A) \subseteq R$ where R is an N_N RSO set of V . Hence $f(A)$ is an N_N RW-closed set of V .

Proposition 4.17: If $f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (V, \tau_N(T))$ is N_N -closed and $g: (V, \tau_N(T)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RW-closed then $g \circ f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RW-closed.

Proof: Let F be an N_N -closed set of neutrosophic nano topological space $(U, \tau_N(S))$. Then $f(F)$ is an N_N -closed set of $(V, \tau_N(T))$. By hypothesis, $g \circ f(F) = g(f(F))$ is an N_N RW-closed set in N_N -topological space W . Thus $g \circ f: (U, \tau_N(S)) \rightarrow (W, \tau_N(R))$ is N_N RW-closed.

Conclusions: In this article, the authors have introduced and studied the concepts such as, Neutrosophic nano RW-closed set, N_N RW-open set, N_N RWT_{1/2} space, N_N RW-connected space, N_N RW-continuous, N_N RW-irresolute, N_N RW-open and N_N -closed maps. In future it can be extended to

some new forms of continuous functions and homeomorphisms.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Acknowledgements: The authors are highly grateful to the Referees for their valuable suggestions.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Received: Nov 1, 2021. Accepted: Feb 5, 2022